

Cruise report 64PE436 – NICO leg 9A

Untangling the topography – hydrography interaction that sustains cold-water coral reefs

Galway - Galway

April 29th – May 10th 2018

Rockall Bank

Chief scientist: Dick van Oevelen

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1. Introduction

1.1 Aim and background

Cruise 64PE436 is a NIOZ contribution to the NWO-funded VIDI project 'Surviving in a Deep-Sea Desert – Uncovering the Functioning of Cold-Water Coral Reefs in the Deep Ocean' awarded to Dick van Oevelen (grant number 864.13.007) and the EU-funded ATLAS program (www.eu-atlas.org) funded to Dick van Oevelen and Gerard Duineveld and is part of the NICO (<https://nico-expeditie.nl/>) program as NICO leg 9A.

The deep seafloor harbors one of the most biodiverse ecosystems on our planet: cold-water coral reefs. Like their tropical counterparts, cold-water corals (CWCs) form structurally complex habitats that support a diverse and productive reef community. It is still paradoxical how such a rich ecosystem can thrive in the deep sea; an environment that is typically considered to be food limited. The VIDI and ATLAS project collectively target this paradox by an integrated study on the delivery, uptake and processing of organic matter by cold-water coral reef communities along Rockall Bank, an area that has amongst the highest abundance of cold-water coral reefs in the world. In this context, two moorings were, amongst others, placed on Rockall bank (± 300 m water depth) and the rich Oreo mound (± 750 m water depth) during cruise 64PE420 (May 2017).

Cruise 64PE436 has the following objectives:

1. *Retrieval of the two long-term moorings that were deployed in May 2017.*
2. *Mapping of the physical and biological regime along an across-slope transect to the coral mounds during the full diurnal cycle. We will monitor surface currents (ship-ADCP), profile the water column with a CTD and sensors for backscatter, fluorimetry and particles sizes (LISST) and take discrete water samples for nutrients, carbonate chemistry, dissolved and particulate organic matter, microzooplankton and mesozooplankton composition and abundance.*
3. *Continuation of the NICO student program*
4. *Deploy a camera-system at selected topographic features to map the cold-water coral distribution in relation to topography and hydrography.*
5. *Outreach activities by writing blogs*

1.2 Scientific crew

Dick van Oevelen, NIOZ	Chief scientist
Christian Mohn, AU	ship ADCP, CTD data processing
Mads Schulz, AU	Multinet sampling for mesozooplankton
Pieter van Rijswijk, NIOZ	CTD team 1 leader
Evert de Froe, NIOZ	CTD team 1
Sandra Maier, NIOZ	CTD team 2 leader
Chiu Cheng, NIOZ	CTD team 2
Henriette Horn, NIOZ	CTD team 3 leader + meso/microzooplankton
Anna van der Kaaden, NIOZ	CTD team 3
Britt van Haastregt, UU	NICO student program + CTD team 2
Evi Wubben, UU	NICO student program + CTD team 2
Edda Heinsman	Freelance journalist

2. Logbook of cruise 64PE436

Transit

Pelagia left the harbor around 16:30u. The clock on the ship will be set to UTC at 2am to correspond to local time and to time on scientific equipment.

April 30th

Stations 1-7

We did a rehearsal station on the transect from Galway to the study so that all activities can be tested by the different CTD teams. The rehearsal routine started after lunch with several CTD yoyo's and then one during which NISKINs were closed. It appeared that the multinet could not be used from the side, because a conversion cable was missing and because the power on the CTD cable is too high for the multinet. The voltage would then need to be modified for each switch between CTD and multinet and this takes 1.5-2 hours to switch, which is too long. Therefore, we decided with the crew that multinet will be used on the A-frame with a slow speed to avoid that the line gets caught in the thrusters. Today it was too late to test it unfortunately.

May 1st

Figure and table with station coordinates for the targeted 24-hour stations.

Planned 24-hour stations	Latitude	Longitude
1 [Deep station]	55 25.69N	015 46.54W
2 [Oreo mound, next to mooring]	55 27.17N	015 52.28W
3 [Haas mound]	55 29.31N	015 47.92W
4 [Ridge]	55 30.45N	015 52.60W
5 [Slope]	55 33.50N	015 54.25W
6 [Bank, next to mooring]	55 38.70N	015 55.94W

Oreo mound (Station 2): Casino stations 8 – 43 (May 2nd to May 3rd)

A headwind caused a serious delay during the last day of the transit. Estimated arrival on the station changed from 8u to 16u. Also decided to go for Oreo mound as first station, because weather conditions may make it tricky to get the moorings out, so we need to do those stations first to give a window of opportunity to get the moorings up whenever possible.

Arrival at Oreo mound at 18.30u where we started the 24-cycle. The first sampling indicated that a duplicate sampling is too demanding for the CTD teams and can only just be finished in time, therefore we decided to go for n=1 for the rest of the sampling.

The sea was too rough for the multinet deployment so we had to cancel that one for the night. The sea calmed down on May 3rd and we did two multinet deployments during the day. One for biomass and one for isotopes. After lunch we did station 39 for the NICO student program and continued with the station program. Program finished around 19.00u after we steamed to the Bank station (Station 6 on map above). The night multinet deployment needed to be skipped because of swell and strong wind. Otherwise program continued as planned.

A summary of the station activities is given below. Details of the Casino stations can be found in Appendix A.

Casino stations	Variables	Time step
#8	Water quality + DIC	T0
#9 #10 #11 #12 #13	Yoyo's	
#14	Water quality	T4
#15	Yoyo's	
Cancelled	Multinet (1x BIO)	
#16 #17 #18 #19 #20	Yoyo's	
#21	Water quality + DIC + μ Zoo	T8
#22 #23 #24 #25 #26 #27	Yoyo's	
#28	Water quality	T12
#29 #30 #31 #32 #33 #34	Yoyo's	
#35	Water quality + DIC	T16
#36	Yoyo	
#37 #38	Multinet (1x BIO + 1x ISO)	
#39	Yoyo + NICO student program	
#40	Water quality + μ Zoo	T20
#41 #42	Yoyo's	
#43	Water quality + DIC	T24

WQ: refers to samples for the water quality parameters dissolved organic matter, nutrients, flow cytometer (2 and 5 mL), pigments and particulate organic matter.

DIC: refers to samples for pH, alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon

μ Zoo: refers to samples for microzooplankton

Bank station: Casino stations 44 – 96 (May 3rd to May 4th)

The second 24-hour station is close to the mooring on the bank. The multinet deployments had to be cancelled again because of heavy swell. Station #73 was aborted for NISKIN sampling because the bottles could not be fired. The problem appeared to be the motor on the CTD. We replaced this one with the spare motor and we could continue after 2-3 hours of delay.

Casino stations	Variables	Time step
#44	Water quality + DIC	T0
#45 #46 #47 #48 #49 #50 #51	Yoyo's	
#52	Water quality + μ Zoo	T4
Cancelled	Multinet	
#53 #54 #55 #56 #57 #58 #59 #60 #61	Yoyo's	
#62	Water quality + DIC	T8
#63 #64 #65 #66 #67 #68 #69 #70 #71 #72	Yoyo's	
#73 failed to take niskins, motor of CTD needed repair	Yoyo's	
#74	Water quality	T12
#75 #76 #77 #78 #79 #80 #81 #82 #83	Yoyo's	
#84	Water quality + DIC + μ Zoo	T16
Cancelled	Multinet (1x BIO + 1x ISO)	
#85 #86 #87 #88	Yoyo's	
#89	Water quality	T20
#90 #91 #92 #93 #94	Yoyo's	
#95	Water quality + DIC	T24
#96	Yoyo	

Multibeam section: (night May 4th to May 5th)

This night was for multibeam work (station #97), mainly focused to fill in the shallower Rockall Bank section on which we did a long transect last year. The coordinates of the targeted block are shown below.

Coordinate	Latitude	Longitude
South West	55 38.7N	16 03.3W
North West	55 50.0N	16 03.3W
North East	55 50.0N	15 54.0W
South East	55 38.7N	15 54.0W

The rectangular box was ± 11 nm in north-south direction and ± 5 nm in east-west direction. Only part of the rectangle was filled during the night. Ship-ADCP was switched off during the multibeam transect.

Slope station: Casino stations 98 – 139 (May 4th to May 5th)

Station 5

Casino stations	Variables	Time step
#98	Water quality + DIC	T0
#99 #100 #101 #102 #103 #104	Yoyo's	

#105	Water quality + μ Zoo	T4
#106 #107 #108 #109 #110 #111	Yoyo's	
#112	Water quality + DIC	T8
#113 (connection cable failure)	Multinet	
#114 #115 #116 #117	Yoyo's	
#118	Water quality	T12
#119 #120 #121 #122 #123	Yoyo's	
#124	Multinet (1x BIO)	
#125	Water quality + DIC + μ Zoo	T16
#126 #127 #128 #129 #130 #131	Yoyo's	
#132	Water quality	T20
#133 #134 #135 #136 #137 #138	Yoyo's	
#139	Water quality + DIC	T24

Casino station #140 – Mooring recovery (May 5th)

After completing the Slope station (St.5), we made a transit to the Bank station (St.6) to recover the mooring in the morning of May 5th. Recovery was successful and mooring was in good shape (light still flashing on the WET LABS sensor). Fouling was visible on the ADCP transducers, WETLABS sensors and AquaDopp (see pictures below).

Casino station #141 and #142 (May 5th)

The good sea and wind conditions allowed us to do multinet cast for biomass at the Bank (St.6) and Slope station (St.5).

Casino station #143 – Mooring recovery (May 5th)

The mooring on Oreo Mound was recovered in the afternoon of May 5th. Recovery was successful and mooring was in good shape (light still flashing on the WET LABS sensor). Minor fouling was visible on the instruments (see pictures below).

Ridge station (St.4): Casino stations 144 – 170 (May 5th to May 6th)

This station is at the foot of the ridge at Rockall Bank. A full 24-cycle will not be possible, because we have to start the return transit in time and we want to get a CTD with samples from the Deep station (St.1). Therefore, the T24 is absent for the Ridge station.

A summary of this station is given in the following Table.

Casino stations	Variables	Time step
#144	Water quality + DIC + μ Zoo	T0
#145	Multinet (1x BIO)	
#146, #147, #148	Yoyo's	
#149	Water quality	T4
#150 #151 #152 #153	Yoyo's	
#154	Water quality + DIC + μ Zoo	T8
#155	Multinet (1x BIO)	
#156 #157 #158 #159	Yoyo's	
#160	Water quality	T12
#161 #162 #163 #164	Yoyo's	
#165	Water quality + DIC	T16
#166 #167 #168 #169	Yoyo's	
#170	Water quality + DIC	T20

Casino station #171 – Deep station (May 7th)

Before the transit to Galway, we decided to do on CTD cast with samples at the Deep station to have an end-member. Surprisingly, we found several fluorescence peaks down to ± 400 m (see figure below). This prompted us to sample several of the deeper fluorescence peaks in addition to the standard scheme of 5 depths (see respective CTD sheet in the appendix below). We also decided to return to the station at Oreo Mound for a final CTD cast with samples.

Casino station #172 – Oreo station (May 7th)
 Final CTD cast with samples at Oreo Mound.

Transit to Galway (May 7th)
 Return started directly after #172 around 12.40 UTC.

End of cruise

4. CTD stations

Christian Mohn

Large-scale oceanographic conditions in the southern Rockall Channel and Rockall Bank have been well studied. This area is commonly considered as one of the key regions for propagation of warm and saline North Atlantic waters to the Arctic Ocean. Upper layer waters (0-400 m) at the entrance of the Rockall Channel are dominated by Eastern North Atlantic Water (ENAW; Harvey, 1982). ENAW is warm and saline mode water formed by winter convection and mixing with saline Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW, 600 – 1200 m) in the inter-gyre Biscay region (Pollard et al., 1996; Holliday et al., 2000). ENAW is partly carried northward by the European Shelf Edge Current (SEC; Pérez et al., 1995). ENAW in the Rockall Channel may be modulated by the occasional input of cooler and fresher Subpolar Mode Water (SPMW, also referred to as Western North Atlantic Water WNAW), a mode water mass of subpolar origin which is carried eastward with the North Atlantic Current (NAC). Observational evidence for such events is sparse, but periods of low upper layer salinities in the Rockall Channel may be regarded as a consequence of increased influence of SPMW and Subarctic Intermediate Water (SAIW), as suggested by several studies (e.g. Ullgren and White, 2010). ENAW was the dominant upper layer water mass at all stations between the wind-mixed layer and 400 m depth. ENAW is characterized by a linear T–S relationship in the temperature range 9 to 12 °C which was also confirmed during this cruise. Its T/S properties are regionally modulated by mixing with colder water at the two deepest stations 2 and 4. Here, the low temperature and low salinity inflection point at the density $\sigma_\theta = 27.3$ indicate the influence of SPMW/SAIW. Further up-slope, a clear SPMW/SAIW inflection point is not present and replaced by an extension of the ENAW.

Harvey, J. (1982). θ -S relationships and water masses in the eastern North Atlantic. *Deep-Sea Research*, 29, 1021-1033.

Holliday, N.P., R.T. Pollard, J.F. Read, Leach, H. (2000). Water mass properties and fluxes in the Rockall Trough, 1975-1998. *Deep-Sea Research I*, 47, 1303-1332.

Pérez, F.F., Ríos, A.F., King, B.A., Pollard, R.T. (1995). Decadal changes of the θ –S relationship of the Eastern North Atlantic Central Water. *Deep-Sea Research I*, 42 (11/12), 1849 – 1864.

Pollard, R.T., Griffiths, M.J., Cunningham, S.A., Read, J.F., Perez, F.F., Rios, A.F. (1996). Vivaldi 1991 - a study of the formation, circulation and ventilation of Eastern North Atlantic Central Water. *Progress in Oceanography*, 37, 167-192.

Ullgren, J.E., White, M. (2010). Water mass interaction at intermediate depths in the southern Rockall Trough, northeastern North Atlantic. *Deep-Sea Research I*, 57, 248 – 257.

Figure 1: T-S relationships from repeated CTD casts at 4 different stations along the slope of the southeastern Rockall Bank

6. Mesozooplankton sampling

Mads Schulz

The multinet was deployed using the A frame from the aft deck, this in general meant that a calm sea was needed for deployment and restricted sampling for some stations. The multinet was used for biomass sampling at study sites 2, 4, 5 and 6. Isotope sampling was carried out at station 2.

The sampling intervals for all station were:

- bottom – 50 mab
- 50 mab – 100 mab
- 100 mab – 100 m
- 100 m – 50 m
- 50 m – surface

Samples were not collected from the true bottom as a multinet is only meant for pelagic sampling, therefore bottom in these intervals means 10 – 20 m above true bottom.

The isotope samples were sorted on board by sieves at sizes:

- 1000 μm
- 400 μm
- 200 μm
- 100 μm

and subsequently stored at -80°C .

Biomass samples were fixed in 4% Formol for storage. During the cruise, three nets were damaged during deployments at station #124, #142 and #155 and the corresponding samples should therefore be regarded as not quantifiable. One deployment did not produce any samples as connection to the device failed due to a broken cable (#113).

Zooplankton was observed at all stations at all depths, but with increasing amount of smaller zooplankton in the upper 100 m, larger zooplankton species were observed during the day below 100 m. This was the case for the biomass and isotope sampling.

<i>Location</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Depth</i>
<i>Oreo mound, #37</i>	<i>Biomass, Day</i>	<i>750</i>
<i>Oreo mound, #38</i>	<i>Isotopes, Day</i>	<i>750</i>
<i>Slope station, #124</i>	<i>Biomass, Night</i>	<i>640</i>

<i>Bank station, #141</i>	<i>Biomass, Day</i>	<i>475</i>
<i>Slope station, #142</i>	<i>Biomass, Day</i>	<i>640</i>
<i>Ridge station, #145</i>	<i>Biomass, Day</i>	<i>824</i>
<i>Ridge station, #155</i>	<i>Biomass, Night</i>	<i>824</i>

8. NICO student program

Britt van Haastregt & Evi Wubben

Notes regarding the NICO student program are noted in the logbook on board.

9. Blogs

Edda Heinsman & Dick van Oevelen

A total of 6 blogs were written by Edda Heinsman:

- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/net-als-kapitein-ortega/>
- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/zeeziek-op-een-onderzoeksschip/>
- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/op-de-eerste-rij-in-gods-theater/>
- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/massamigratie-in-de-oceaan/>
- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/als-een-geoliede-machine/>
- <https://www.nemokennislink.nl/publicaties/het-einde-van-deze-expeditie-is-nog-maar-het-begin-van-het-onderzoek/>

Appendices

Cruise	64PE436		CTD team	PvR, CC
Date	03/05/2018		CTD operator	Dick
Station	35			
Depth	750m			
Type				

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight	
1	5mab	745	8.6	-69.8		X	X					4	123.16	4	
2	5mab	745	8.6												
3	50mab	702	8.7	-70.4		X	X					4	122.83	4	
4	50mab	702	8.7												
5	375 mab	375	9.3	-69.1		X	X					4	122.61	4	
6	375 mab	375	9.3												
7	50mbs	50	9.9	-72.3		X	X					4	121.01	2	
8	50mbs	50	9.9												
9	5mbs	3	9.9	-72.9		X	X					3	123.52	2	
10	5mbs	3	9.9												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

pH Cal
ph4=152.7
ph7=-10.3
Tris=-99.5

Cruise	64PE436		CTD team	Britt en Evi
Date	03/05/2018		CTD operator	Christian / Anna
Station	39			
Depth	750m			
Type	NICO student program			

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight	
1	200	200													
2	90	88													
3	38	38													
4	38	38													
5	38	38													
6	15	13.8													
7	15	13.8													
8	15	13.8													
9	15	13.8													
10	3	3.3													
11	3	3.3													
12	3	3.3													
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Date	03/05/2018		CTD team			Pieter, Chiu								
Station	44		CTD operator			Dick								
Depth	473 m													
Type	Station 6 - Bank													

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μ Zoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL	vol [L]	weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	470	8.6		-66.5							4	124.2	4	
2	5mab	470	8.6												
3	50mab	421	8.7		-66.9						4	123.17	4		
4	50mab	421	8.7												
5	375 mab	236	9.4		-68.8						4	123.49	4		
6	375 mab	236	9.4												
7	50mbs	40	10.0		-72.4						4	121.61	4		
8	50mbs	40	10.0												
9	5mbs	5.5	10.0		-73.2						4	122.99	4		
10	5mbs	5.5	10.0												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

pH Cal
 ph4=154.0
 ph7=-8.6
 Tris=-98.1

Cruise	64PE436		CTD team			Sandra								
Date	03/05/2018		CTD operator			Christian								
Station	52													
Depth	470 m													
Type														

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μ Zoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL	vol [L]	weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	468	8.6					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	5	121.92	4	SRM
2	5mab	468	8.6												
3	50mab	422	8.7					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	5	124	4	SRM
4	50mab	422	8.7												
5	mw	235	9.4					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	5	124.98	4	SRM
6	mw	235	9.4												
7	dcm	49	10.0					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	124.33	4	SRM
8	dcm	49	10.0												
9	5m	5.8	10.0					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	123.12	3	SRM
10	5m	5.8	10.0												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Cruise		64PE436															
Date		03/05/2018															
Station		62															
Depth		470 m															
Type																	
		CTD team										Evert, Henriette					
		CTD operator										Christian					
Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo	pH4: 151.6 pH7: -11.2 Tris: -9.9	
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight			vol [L]
1	5mab		8.61		8.115	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	122.02	4	SRM		
2	5mab		8.61														
3	50mab	421	8.6												SRM		
4	50mab	421	8.6		8.15	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	122.58	4			
5	mw	235	9.3		8.182	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	124.08	4	SRM		
6	mw	235	9.3														
7	dcm	53	10.0		8.235	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	3	121.76	4	SRM		
8	dcm	53	10.0														
9	5m	5.3	10.0		8.209	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	3	124.43	3	SRM		
10	5m	5.3	10.0														
11																	
12																	
13																	
14																	
15																	
16																	
17																	
18																	
19																	
20																	
21																	
22																	
23																	
24																	

Cruise		64PE436															
Date		04/05/2018															
Station		74															
Depth		475 m															
Type																	
		CTD team										Evi, Pieter, Chiu, Sandra					
		CTD operator										Dick					
Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo		
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight			vol [L]
1	5mab	465	8.8					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	120.48	4			
2	5mab	465	8.8														
3	50mab	422	8.8					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	121.57	4			
4	50mab	422	8.8														
5	mw	236	9.1					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	121.53	4			
6	mw	236	9.1														
7	dcm	50	9.9					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	124.05	4			
8	dcm	50	9.9														
9	5m	3.5	10.0					SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	124.01	4			
10	5m	3.5	10.0														
11																	
12																	
13																	
14																	
15																	
16																	
17																	
18																	
19																	
20																	
21																	
22																	
23																	
24																	

Cruise	64PE436																	
Date	05/05/2018				CTD team		Britt, Sandra											
Station	105				CTD operator		Dick											
Depth	650m																	
Type																		

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments vol [L]	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	637													
2	5mab	637						SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	123.72	5	SRM
3	50mab	596													
4	50mab	596						SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	122.93	4	SRM
5	mw	325						SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3.25	123.74	5	SRM
6	mw	325													
7	dcm	45						SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	124.52	4	SRM
8	dcm	45													
9	5m	5						SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	126.34	4	SRM
10	5m	5													
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Cruise	64PE436																	
Date	05/05/2018				CTD team		EdF											
Station	112				CTD operator		Christian, Anna											
Depth	640																	
Type																		

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments vol [L]	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	642	8.31		-64.8	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	123.83	4	
2	5mab	642	8.31												
3	50mab	588	8.35		-64.9	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	125.32	4	
4	50mab	588	8.35												
5	mw	319	8.99		-66	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	4	125.05	4	
6	mw	319	8.99												
7	dcm	30.5	9.93		-67.9	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	3	126.01	3	
8	dcm	30.5	9.93												
9	5m	5	9.96		-69.2	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF	3	122.31	3	
10	5m	5	9.96												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

pH4: 153.6
pH7: -10.1
Tris: -100.4

Cruise	64PE436																	
Date	05/05/2018	20:40				CTD team												
Station	118					CTD operator	Christian, Anna											
Depth	640																	
Type																		

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments vol [L]	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	642	8.22					x	x	x	x	4	123.82	4	
2	5mab	642	8.22												
3	50mab	589	8.22					x	x	x	x	4	122.88	4	
4	50mab	589	8.22												
5	mw	319	9.07					x	x	x	x	4	125.66	4	
6	mw	319	9.07												
7	dcm	40	9.93					x	x	x	x	3	122.26	4	
8	dcm	40	9.93												
9	5m	5.4	9.94					x	x	x	x	3	122.28	4	
10	5m	5.4	9.94												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Cruise	64PE436																	
Date	05/05/2018	20:40				CTD team	Sandra											
Station	125					CTD operator	Christian, Dick											
Depth	650																	
Type																		

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments vol [L]	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		weight	vol [L]	
1	5mab	638	8.11		-66.5	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	124	4	SRM
2	5mab	638	8.11												
3	50mab	590	8.24		-67.3	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	124.15	4	SRM
4	50mab	590	8.24												
5	mw	321	8.92		-68.1	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	4	122.89	4	SRM
6	mw	321	8.92												
7	dcm	16	9.91		-74	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	122.9	3	SRM
8	dcm	16	9.91												
9	5m	5.3	9.90		-74.6	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	SRM	3	121.38	3	SRM
10	5m	5.3	9.90												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

pH4: 154.8
pH7: -10.4
Tris: -100.9

Cruise	64PE436													
Date	07/05/2018			CTD team	Evert, Jette					pH4=154.8				
Time	05:30			CTD operator	Jan					pH7=-11.6				
Station	165									tris=-102.2				
Depth	820													

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight	
1	5mab	815	8.3		-67.0	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF			5	126.07	4	
2	5mab	815	8.3		JH										
3	50mab	769	8.4		-67.6	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF			5	123.73	4	
4	50mab	769	8.4												
5	mw	410	9.20		-68.8	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF			5	124.05	4	
6	mw	410	9.20												
7	dcm1	32	10.40		-73.2	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF			3	123.21	4	
8	dcm1	32	10.40												
9	5m	6.1	10.50		-73.2	EdF	EdF	EdF	EdF			4	124.43	3	
10	5m	6.1	10.50												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Cruise	64PE436													
Date	07/05/2018			CTD team	Pieter / Chiu						pH4=154			
Time	09:00			CTD operator	Dick/Anna						pH7=-10.1			
Station	170										tris=-101.4			
Depth	820													

Bottle	Depth (ID)	Depth (m)	Temp	pH		DIC	Alkalinity	NUTS	DOC	FlowCyt		Pigments	sPOM		μZoo
				need?	Value					2 mL	5 mL		vol [L]	weight	
1	5mab	820	8.21		-68.8							4	123.51	4	
2	5mab	820	8.21												
3	50mab	774	8.47		-68.8							4	123.45	4	
4	50mab	774	8.47												
5	mw	407	9.17		-70.0							4	124.86	4	
6	mw	407	9.17												
7	dcm1	11	10.44		-74.7							3	124.73	4	
8	dcm1	11	10.44												
9	5m	5	10.44		-74.7							3	123.04	4	
10	5m	5	10.44												
11															
12															
13															
14															
15															
16															
17															
18															
19															
20															
21															
22															
23															
24															

Appendix 2 – Casino logbook

Date	Heure	Latitude (degre minutes)	Longitude (degre minutes)	Phase name	Type	Device name	Action name
30/04/2018	16:46:11	53.2269	-9.1476	TRANSIT1	PHA		
01/05/2018	13:11:21	54.3596	-12.9334	STATION1	PHA		
01/05/2018	13:15:37	54.3596	-12.9332		OPE	CTD	Begin
01/05/2018	13:26:00	54.3595	-12.9331		OPE	CTD	Bottom
01/05/2018	13:36:11	54.3595	-12.9335		OPE	CTD	End
01/05/2018	13:36:23	54.3595	-12.9336	STATION2	PHA		
01/05/2018	13:42:45	54.3595	-12.9338		OPE	CTD	Begin
01/05/2018	13:50:21	54.3594	-12.934		OPE	CTD	Bottom
01/05/2018	13:58:21	54.3595	-12.9343		OPE	CTD	End
01/05/2018	14:06:17	54.3597	-12.9351	STATION3	PHA		
01/05/2018	14:08:17	54.3598	-12.9353		OPE	CTD	Begin
01/05/2018	14:17:41	54.3597	-12.9357		OPE	CTD	Bottom
01/05/2018	14:26:33	54.3598	-12.9357		OPE	CTD	End
01/05/2018	14:31:54	54.3597	-12.9358	STATION4	PHA		
01/05/2018	14:33:41	54.3597	-12.9358		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
01/05/2018	14:43:05	54.3597	-12.9357		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
01/05/2018	15:03:11	54.3597	-12.9355		OPE	CTD with samples	End
01/05/2018	16:32:53	54.3614	-12.9339	STATION5	PHA		
01/05/2018	16:37:20	54.3614	-12.9342		OPE	CTD	Begin
01/05/2018	16:47:34	54.3617	-12.9349		OPE	CTD	Bottom
01/05/2018	16:55:10	54.3617	-12.9352		OPE	CTD	End
01/05/2018	16:58:24	54.3617	-12.9355	STATION6	PHA		
01/05/2018	17:02:59	54.362	-12.9355		OPE	CTD	Begin
01/05/2018	17:10:56	54.362	-12.9358		OPE	CTD	Bottom
01/05/2018	17:19:22	54.3623	-12.9358		OPE	CTD	End
01/05/2018	17:21:37	54.3622	-12.9359	STATION7	PHA		

01/05/2018	17:27:12	54.3621	-12.9358		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
01/05/2018	17:33:14	54.362	-12.9355		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
01/05/2018	17:48:51	54.3621	-12.9352		OPE	CTD with samples	End
01/05/2018	17:53:59	54.3624	-12.9344	TRANSIT2	PHA		
02/05/2018	18:27:34	55.4527	-15.8702	STATION8	PHA		
02/05/2018	18:36:28	55.453	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
02/05/2018	18:49:39	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
02/05/2018	19:08:48	55.4529	-15.8715		OPE	CTD with samples	End
02/05/2018	19:33:03	55.4529	-15.8714	STATION9	PHA		
02/05/2018	19:36:24	55.453	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	19:50:34	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	20:05:17	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	20:05:28	55.4529	-15.8711	STATION10	PHA		
02/05/2018	20:05:57	55.4529	-15.871		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	20:19:47	55.4531	-15.8709		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	20:35:01	55.4531	-15.871		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	20:35:11	55.4531	-15.871	STATION11	PHA		
02/05/2018	20:35:55	55.4532	-15.8706		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	20:49:44	55.453	-15.8708		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	21:05:00	55.4531	-15.8708		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	21:05:08	55.4531	-15.8708	STATION12	PHA		
02/05/2018	21:06:29	55.453	-15.871		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	21:20:00	55.4529	-15.8708		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	21:34:07	55.4529	-15.8709		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	21:34:16	55.453	-15.8709	STATION13	PHA		

02/05/2018	21:35:25	55.453	-15.8707		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	21:48:44	55.453	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	22:02:52	55.453	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	22:03:00	55.453	-15.8712	STATION14	PHA		
02/05/2018	22:03:59	55.4531	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
02/05/2018	22:17:11	55.453	-15.8712		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
02/05/2018	22:42:13	55.453	-15.871		OPE	CTD with samples	End
02/05/2018	22:42:23	55.453	-15.871	STATION15	PHA		
02/05/2018	23:03:57	55.4528	-15.871		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	23:17:06	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Bottom
02/05/2018	23:33:16	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	End
02/05/2018	23:33:25	55.4529	-15.8712	STATION16	PHA		
02/05/2018	23:35:37	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
02/05/2018	23:47:53	55.453	-15.8709		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	00:04:24	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	00:04:31	55.4529	-15.8713	STATION17	PHA		
03/05/2018	00:06:00	55.453	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	00:20:04	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	00:36:19	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	00:36:27	55.4528	-15.8713	STATION18	PHA		
03/05/2018	00:37:58	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	00:50:55	55.453	-15.8717		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	01:06:42	55.4528	-15.8715		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	01:06:50	55.4528	-15.8715	STATION19	PHA		
03/05/2018	01:08:12	55.4528	-15.8715		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	01:21:49	55.4529	-15.871		OPE	CTD	Bottom

03/05/2018	01:36:41	55.4531	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	01:36:57	55.4531	-15.8712	STATION20	PHA		
03/05/2018	01:38:19	55.4533	-15.8709		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	01:52:05	55.4528	-15.8717		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	02:07:15	55.4531	-15.871		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	02:07:36	55.4531	-15.871	STATION21	PHA		
03/05/2018	02:09:00	55.453	-15.8709		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	02:22:45	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	02:50:02	55.4529	-15.8709		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	03:22:50	55.4534	-15.8707	STATION22	PHA		
03/05/2018	03:29:28	55.4527	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	03:45:22	55.4528	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	04:00:51	55.4526	-15.8709		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	04:00:58	55.4526	-15.8709	STATION23	PHA		
03/05/2018	04:02:19	55.4527	-15.8708		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	04:16:08	55.4525	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	04:30:10	55.4525	-15.8716		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	04:30:16	55.4525	-15.8716	STATION24	PHA		
03/05/2018	04:31:01	55.4526	-15.8716		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	04:44:07	55.4528	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	04:57:55	55.4528	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	04:58:40	55.4529	-15.8712	STATION25	PHA		
03/05/2018	04:58:48	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	05:12:15	55.4528	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	05:25:45	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	05:26:17	55.4528	-15.8713	STATION26	PHA		

03/05/2018	05:26:31	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	05:40:25	55.4529	-15.8715		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	05:53:42	55.4528	-15.8715		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	05:54:30	55.4528	-15.8715	STATION27	PHA		
03/05/2018	05:54:43	55.4529	-15.8715		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	06:08:35	55.4528	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	06:22:28	55.453	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	06:23:00	55.453	-15.8712	STATION28	PHA		
03/05/2018	06:23:52	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	06:36:54	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	06:59:23	55.4528	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	07:21:52	55.453	-15.8709	STATION29	PHA		
03/05/2018	07:24:45	55.4528	-15.8706		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	07:37:40	55.4529	-15.871		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	07:51:33	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	07:51:37	55.4529	-15.8713	STATION30	PHA		
03/05/2018	07:52:24	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	08:05:10	55.4531	-15.8717		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	08:18:39	55.4527	-15.871		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	08:18:57	55.4527	-15.871	STATION31	PHA		
03/05/2018	08:20:02	55.4526	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	08:32:55	55.4528	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	08:46:57	55.4526	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	08:47:06	55.4526	-15.8714	STATION32	PHA		
03/05/2018	08:47:58	55.4527	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	09:00:53	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Bottom

03/05/2018	09:14:13	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	09:14:23	55.4529	-15.8713	STATION33	PHA		
03/05/2018	09:15:17	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	09:28:42	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	09:42:43	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	09:42:54	55.4529	-15.8712	STATION34	PHA		
03/05/2018	09:44:06	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	09:57:14	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	10:11:25	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	10:11:36	55.4529	-15.8713	STATION35	PHA		
03/05/2018	10:13:11	55.4528	-15.8712		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	10:26:16	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	10:48:01	55.4531	-15.8712		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	10:48:12	55.4531	-15.8712	STATION36	PHA		
03/05/2018	11:12:33	55.4531	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	11:26:05	55.4531	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	11:39:13	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	11:39:24	55.4529	-15.8711	STATION37	PHA		
03/05/2018	12:02:57	55.453	-15.8717		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
03/05/2018	12:32:37	55.4531	-15.8721		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
03/05/2018	13:00:16	55.4535	-15.8719		OPE	MultiNet	End
03/05/2018	13:25:43	55.4529	-15.8707	STATION38	PHA		
03/05/2018	13:39:23	55.4531	-15.8703		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
03/05/2018	14:16:16	55.4538	-15.8714		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
03/05/2018	14:44:11	55.4536	-15.8708		OPE	MultiNet	End

03/05/2018	14:45:07	55.4536	-15.8705	STATION39	PHA		
03/05/2018	14:53:37	55.453	-15.8712		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	15:10:18	55.453	-15.871		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	15:37:56	55.4532	-15.8707		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	16:09:24	55.4529	-15.871	STATION40	PHA		
03/05/2018	16:12:20	55.453	-15.8709		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	16:25:44	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	16:53:29	55.4528	-15.8713		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	17:12:39	55.4528	-15.8714	STATION41	PHA		
03/05/2018	17:15:28	55.4529	-15.8714		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	17:30:46	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	17:49:30	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	17:50:25	55.4529	-15.8713	STATION42	PHA		
03/05/2018	17:52:25	55.4529	-15.8713		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	18:06:27	55.4529	-15.8712		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	18:20:33	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	18:21:04	55.4529	-15.871	STATION43	PHA		
03/05/2018	18:21:39	55.4529	-15.871		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	18:35:51	55.4529	-15.8711		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	19:01:15	55.453	-15.871		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	19:03:51	55.453	-15.8711	TRANSIT3	PHA		
03/05/2018	20:46:15	55.6459	-15.9314	STATION44	PHA		

03/05/2018	20:51:58	55.6452	-15.932		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
03/05/2018	21:00:38	55.6449	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
03/05/2018	21:18:15	55.6452	-15.932		OPE	CTD with samples	End
03/05/2018	21:18:33	55.6452	-15.932	STATION45	PHA		
03/05/2018	21:44:29	55.645	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	21:53:10	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	22:01:51	55.6451	-15.9318		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	22:01:59	55.645	-15.9318	STATION46	PHA		
03/05/2018	22:02:54	55.6449	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	22:11:18	55.6455	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	22:20:22	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	22:20:33	55.6451	-15.9323	STATION47	PHA		
03/05/2018	22:21:39	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	22:29:56	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	22:38:47	55.6449	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	22:38:55	55.6449	-15.9323	STATION48	PHA		
03/05/2018	22:39:50	55.6449	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	22:48:14	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	22:56:59	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	22:57:10	55.645	-15.9321	STATION49	PHA		
03/05/2018	22:58:07	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	23:06:33	55.645	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	23:15:36	55.6452	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	23:15:48	55.6452	-15.9322	STATION50	PHA		
03/05/2018	23:16:44	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	23:24:59	55.645	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	Bottom

03/05/2018	23:33:51	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	23:34:01	55.645	-15.9325	STATION51	PHA		
03/05/2018	23:35:00	55.6449	-15.9326		OPE	CTD	Begin
03/05/2018	23:43:16	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
03/05/2018	23:52:14	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	CTD	End
03/05/2018	23:52:25	55.645	-15.9319	STATION52	PHA		
03/05/2018	23:54:05	55.6452	-15.9319		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	00:02:34	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	00:19:57	55.6452	-15.9318		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	00:20:20	55.6452	-15.9318	STATION53	PHA		
04/05/2018	00:39:09	55.6453	-15.9313		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	00:49:52	55.6448	-15.9318		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	00:59:03	55.6447	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	00:59:10	55.6447	-15.9327	STATION54	PHA		
04/05/2018	01:00:58	55.6446	-15.933		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	01:09:36	55.6449	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	01:18:48	55.6452	-15.933		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	01:18:54	55.6452	-15.933	STATION55	PHA		
04/05/2018	01:20:25	55.6453	-15.9329		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	01:28:53	55.6454	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	01:38:02	55.6453	-15.9318		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	01:38:07	55.6453	-15.9318	STATION56	PHA		
04/05/2018	01:39:52	-100	-200		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	01:48:18	55.6448	-15.9316		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	01:57:11	55.6448	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	01:57:16	55.6448	-15.9327	STATION57	PHA		

04/05/2018	01:58:42	55.6447	-15.9328		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	02:07:01	55.6449	-15.9332		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	02:16:54	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	02:17:02	55.6452	-15.9323	STATION58	PHA		
04/05/2018	02:18:25	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	02:26:56	55.6451	-15.9326		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	02:36:00	55.6448	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	02:36:07	55.6448	-15.9325	STATION59	PHA		
04/05/2018	02:37:34	55.6449	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	02:45:44	55.6449	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	02:54:49	55.6452	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	02:54:56	55.6452	-15.9324	STATION60	PHA		
04/05/2018	02:56:58	-100	-200		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	03:04:37	55.6454	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	03:13:35	55.645	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	03:13:41	55.645	-15.9327	STATION61	PHA		
04/05/2018	03:14:59	55.6452	-15.9328		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	03:23:16	55.6451	-15.9329		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	03:32:24	55.6449	-15.9319		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	03:32:29	55.6449	-15.9319	STATION62	PHA		
04/05/2018	03:33:53	55.645	-15.9319		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	03:42:30	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	04:01:34	55.6457	-15.9321		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	04:33:22	55.645	-15.9322	STATION63	PHA		
04/05/2018	04:35:38	55.645	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	04:44:45	55.6449	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Bottom

04/05/2018	04:53:41	55.6452	-15.932		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	04:53:51	55.6452	-15.932	STATION64	PHA		
04/05/2018	04:54:48	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	05:03:46	55.6451	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	05:13:38	55.6452	-15.9319		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	05:13:44	55.6452	-15.9319	STATION65	PHA		
04/05/2018	05:14:42	55.6452	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	05:23:26	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	05:33:09	55.645	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	05:33:15	55.645	-15.9321	STATION66	PHA		
04/05/2018	05:33:56	55.645	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	05:42:29	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	05:52:26	55.6449	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	05:52:34	55.645	-15.9324	STATION67	PHA		
04/05/2018	05:53:29	55.6449	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	06:02:19	55.6452	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	06:12:54	55.6451	-15.932		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	06:12:58	55.6451	-15.932	STATION68	PHA		
04/05/2018	06:13:42	55.645	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	06:22:44	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	06:32:44	55.6451	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	06:32:50	55.6451	-15.9325	STATION69	PHA		
04/05/2018	06:33:51	55.645	-15.9326		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	06:42:00	55.645	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	06:52:02	55.6452	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	06:52:07	55.6452	-15.9325	STATION70	PHA		
04/05/2018	06:52:45	55.6452	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	07:03:23	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom

04/05/2018	07:10:39	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	07:10:44	55.6452	-15.9323	STATION71	PHA		
04/05/2018	07:11:31	55.6451	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	07:20:16	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	07:29:28	55.645	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	07:29:33	55.645	-15.9324	STATION72	PHA		
04/05/2018	07:30:19	55.6449	-15.9326		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	07:39:21	55.6452	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	07:48:58	55.6449	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	07:49:02	55.6449	-15.9324	STATION73	PHA		
04/05/2018	07:49:32	55.6449	-15.9324		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	07:58:55	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	08:13:35	55.6453	-15.9323		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	08:13:50	55.6453	-15.9323	STATION74	PHA		
04/05/2018	11:05:18	55.6452	-15.9317		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	11:14:23	55.6451	-15.9327		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	11:33:17	55.6449	-15.9324		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	11:34:02	55.6448	-15.9324	STATION75	PHA		
04/05/2018	11:59:39	55.6449	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	12:07:54	55.6448	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	12:16:46	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	12:16:59	55.645	-15.932	STATION76	PHA		
04/05/2018	12:18:12	55.6452	-15.9319		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	12:26:51	55.6448	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	12:35:42	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End

04/05/2018	12:35:49	55.6451	-15.9321	STATION77	PHA		
04/05/2018	12:37:14	55.6452	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	12:46:26	55.6451	-15.9319		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	12:55:04	55.6447	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	12:55:09	55.6447	-15.9322	STATION78	PHA		
04/05/2018	12:57:18	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	13:05:04	55.645	-15.9328		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	13:13:56	55.6449	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	13:14:00	55.6449	-15.9322	STATION79	PHA		
04/05/2018	13:15:27	55.6448	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	13:23:45	55.6448	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	13:32:43	55.6449	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	13:32:49	55.6449	-15.9324	STATION80	PHA		
04/05/2018	13:34:26	55.6447	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	13:42:44	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	13:51:20	55.6452	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	13:51:27	55.6452	-15.9324	STATION81	PHA		
04/05/2018	13:52:49	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	14:00:50	55.6454	-15.9326		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	14:09:31	55.6449	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	14:09:38	55.6449	-15.9327	STATION82	PHA		
04/05/2018	14:10:34	55.6449	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	14:19:39	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	14:28:20	55.6448	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	14:28:27	55.6448	-15.9323	STATION83	PHA		
04/05/2018	14:30:44	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	14:39:31	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	14:48:30	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	End

04/05/2018	14:48:36	55.645	-15.9322	STATION84	PHA		
04/05/2018	14:50:37	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	14:58:57	55.6449	-15.9326		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	15:17:53	55.6454	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	15:42:10	55.6448	-15.9329	STATION85	PHA		
04/05/2018	15:44:42	55.6449	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	15:54:41	55.6451	-15.9327		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	16:03:39	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	16:03:47	55.645	-15.9324	STATION86	PHA		
04/05/2018	16:05:27	55.645	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	16:13:49	55.645	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	16:22:51	55.6451	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	16:22:57	55.6451	-15.9325	STATION87	PHA		
04/05/2018	16:24:56	55.645	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	16:33:09	55.6452	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	16:42:19	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	16:42:24	55.6451	-15.9321	STATION88	PHA		
04/05/2018	16:43:30	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	16:51:39	55.645	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	17:01:10	55.645	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	17:01:15	55.645	-15.9325	STATION89	PHA		
04/05/2018	17:02:46	55.6451	-15.9325		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	17:11:04	55.645	-15.9323		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	17:28:57	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	17:29:02	55.6451	-15.9321	STATION90	PHA		

04/05/2018	18:05:29	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	18:15:52	55.6452	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	18:24:31	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	18:24:38	55.6451	-15.9324	STATION91	PHA		
04/05/2018	18:26:06	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	18:34:55	55.645	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	18:43:54	55.6451	-15.932		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	18:43:59	55.6451	-15.932	STATION92	PHA		
04/05/2018	18:45:16	55.6451	-15.932		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	18:53:34	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	19:02:24	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	19:02:33	55.6451	-15.9321	STATION93	PHA		
04/05/2018	19:03:39	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	19:11:56	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	19:21:08	55.6451	-15.9324		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	19:22:40	-100	-200	STATION94	PHA		
04/05/2018	19:22:57	-100	-200		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	19:30:47	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD	Bottom
04/05/2018	19:39:50	55.6451	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	19:39:55	55.6451	-15.9323	STATION95	PHA		
04/05/2018	19:41:13	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
04/05/2018	19:50:15	55.645	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
04/05/2018	20:07:36	55.6451	-15.9322		OPE	CTD with samples	End
04/05/2018	20:13:04	55.6451	-15.9322	STATION96	PHA		
04/05/2018	20:31:39	55.6451	-15.9321		OPE	CTD	Begin
04/05/2018	20:40:02	55.6451	-15.9325		OPE	CTD	Bottom

04/05/2018	20:49:44	55.6452	-15.9323		OPE	CTD	End
04/05/2018	20:49:54	55.6451	-15.9323	STATION97	PHA		
04/05/2018	21:56:32	55.6483	-16.055		OPE	Multibeam	Begin
05/05/2018	06:44:16	55.6446	-16.029		OPE	Multibeam	End
05/05/2018	06:44:23	55.6445	-16.029	TRANSIT4	PHA		
05/05/2018	08:08:02	55.5588	-15.9039	STATION98	PHA		
05/05/2018	08:18:37	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
05/05/2018	08:30:41	55.5586	-15.9039		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
05/05/2018	08:51:52	55.5585	-15.9038		OPE	CTD with samples	End
05/05/2018	08:52:00	55.5585	-15.9038	STATION99	PHA		
05/05/2018	09:21:37	55.5584	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	09:33:25	55.5586	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	09:45:36	55.5584	-15.9037		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	09:45:47	55.5584	-15.9037	STATION100	PHA		
05/05/2018	09:46:45	55.5584	-15.9037		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	09:58:32	55.5586	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	10:10:30	55.5583	-15.9048		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	10:10:41	55.5583	-15.9048	STATION101	PHA		
05/05/2018	10:11:34	55.5585	-15.905		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	10:22:31	55.5584	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	10:34:31	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	10:34:40	55.5584	-15.9043	STATION102	PHA		
05/05/2018	10:35:40	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	10:46:44	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	10:58:24	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	10:58:37	55.5583	-15.9041	STATION103	PHA		

05/05/2018	10:59:39	55.5585	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	11:10:48	55.5585	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	11:22:53	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	11:23:06	55.5583	-15.9042	STATION104	PHA		
05/05/2018	11:24:04	55.5582	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	11:35:42	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	11:47:37	55.5582	-15.9038		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	11:47:47	55.5582	-15.9038	STATION105	PHA		
05/05/2018	11:48:44	55.5581	-15.904		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
05/05/2018	12:00:20	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
05/05/2018	12:24:36	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD with samples	End
05/05/2018	12:54:33	55.558	-15.9042	STATION106	PHA		
05/05/2018	12:57:58	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	13:10:43	55.5586	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	13:23:59	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	13:24:04	55.5583	-15.9041	STATION107	PHA		
05/05/2018	13:26:22	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	13:38:46	55.5582	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	13:52:32	55.558	-15.9037		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	13:52:43	55.558	-15.9037	STATION108	PHA		
05/05/2018	13:53:56	55.5582	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	14:04:53	55.5584	-15.9038		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	14:18:18	55.5584	-15.9038		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	14:19:03	55.5584	-15.9036	STATION109	PHA		
05/05/2018	14:19:46	55.5584	-15.9036		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	14:32:33	55.5583	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Bottom

05/05/2018	14:45:14	55.5583	-15.9036		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	14:45:18	55.5582	-15.9037	STATION110	PHA		
05/05/2018	14:46:28	55.5581	-15.9037		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	14:59:34	55.5583	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	15:12:29	55.558	-15.9036		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	15:12:34	55.558	-15.9036	STATION111	PHA		
05/05/2018	15:13:36	55.5578	-15.9035		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	15:25:54	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	15:39:06	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	15:39:11	55.5583	-15.9042	STATION112	PHA		
05/05/2018	15:40:29	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
05/05/2018	15:51:46	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
05/05/2018	16:17:05	55.5583	-15.9039		OPE	CTD with samples	End
05/05/2018	16:52:29	55.5585	-15.9039	STATION113	PHA		
05/05/2018	16:58:31	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
05/05/2018	17:18:22	55.559	-15.9044		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
05/05/2018	17:37:14	55.5593	-15.9047		OPE	MultiNet	End
05/05/2018	17:44:15	55.5585	-15.9041	STATION114	PHA		
05/05/2018	17:56:29	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	18:08:12	55.5582	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	18:21:41	55.5585	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	18:21:46	55.5585	-15.9042	STATION115	PHA		
05/05/2018	18:22:31	55.5585	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	18:34:04	55.5584	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	18:47:20	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	18:47:27	55.5583	-15.904	STATION116	PHA		

05/05/2018	18:49:40	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	19:00:51	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	19:13:53	55.5582	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	19:13:57	55.5582	-15.9044	STATION117	PHA		
05/05/2018	19:15:24	55.5582	-15.9046		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	19:26:48	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	19:39:53	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	19:39:58	55.5583	-15.904	STATION118	PHA		
05/05/2018	19:41:14	55.5582	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
05/05/2018	19:53:02	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
05/05/2018	20:17:04	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD with samples	End
05/05/2018	20:17:17	55.5583	-15.9041	STATION119	PHA		
05/05/2018	20:39:26	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	20:51:07	55.5584	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	21:02:49	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	21:03:01	55.5584	-15.9043	STATION120	PHA		
05/05/2018	21:03:57	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	21:15:57	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	21:28:01	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	21:28:12	55.5583	-15.9042	STATION121	PHA		
05/05/2018	21:29:18	55.5582	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	21:40:18	55.5582	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	21:52:15	55.5582	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	21:52:23	55.5582	-15.9045	STATION122	PHA		
05/05/2018	21:53:22	55.5581	-15.9046		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	22:04:25	55.5585	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom

05/05/2018	22:16:37	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	22:16:56	55.5585	-15.9043	STATION123	PHA		
05/05/2018	22:17:58	55.5585	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Begin
05/05/2018	22:30:00	55.5582	-15.9045		OPE	CTD	Bottom
05/05/2018	22:41:58	55.5582	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
05/05/2018	22:42:12	55.5582	-15.904	STATION124	PHA		
05/05/2018	23:02:29	55.5584	-15.9039		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
05/05/2018	23:24:02	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
05/05/2018	23:46:09	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	MultiNet	End
05/05/2018	23:46:22	55.5583	-15.9042	STATION125	PHA		
05/05/2018	23:57:58	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	00:09:01	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2018	00:30:48	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	00:55:21	55.5585	-15.9043	STATION126	PHA		
06/05/2018	00:59:45	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	01:11:41	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	01:23:30	55.5582	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	01:24:13	55.5581	-15.9038	STATION127	PHA		
06/05/2018	01:24:54	55.5581	-15.9038		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	01:35:46	55.5581	-15.9045		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	01:47:56	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	01:48:04	55.5584	-15.9043	STATION128	PHA		
06/05/2018	01:49:24	55.5583	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	02:00:17	55.5585	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	02:12:16	55.558	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	02:12:21	55.558	-15.904	STATION129	PHA		

06/05/2018	02:13:57	-100	-200		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	02:24:46	55.5581	-15.904		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	02:36:54	55.5583	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	02:36:58	55.5583	-15.9039	STATION130	PHA		
06/05/2018	02:38:36	55.5583	-15.9039		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	02:49:32	55.5582	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	03:01:38	55.5582	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	03:01:42	55.5582	-15.9043	STATION131	PHA		
06/05/2018	03:03:43	-100	-200		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	03:14:15	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	03:25:58	55.5585	-15.904		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	03:26:03	55.5585	-15.9041	STATION132	PHA		
06/05/2018	03:27:54	55.5584	-15.9041		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	03:39:35	55.5585	-15.904		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2018	04:00:36	55.5585	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	04:23:53	55.5584	-15.9044	STATION133	PHA		
06/05/2018	04:28:02	55.5584	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	04:39:37	55.5585	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	04:53:05	55.5584	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	04:53:09	55.5584	-15.9044	STATION134	PHA		
06/05/2018	04:54:13	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	05:05:47	55.5583	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	05:19:13	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	05:19:18	55.5583	-15.9043	STATION135	PHA		
06/05/2018	05:22:01	55.5584	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	05:31:40	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom

06/05/2018	05:45:10	55.5584	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	05:45:14	55.5584	-15.9041	STATION136	PHA		
06/05/2018	05:46:18	55.5584	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	05:58:16	55.5583	-15.9043		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	06:11:13	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	06:11:49	55.5584	-15.9042	STATION137	PHA		
06/05/2018	06:12:31	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	06:23:55	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	06:36:50	55.5585	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	06:36:54	55.5585	-15.9044	STATION138	PHA		
06/05/2018	06:37:57	55.5585	-15.9044		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	06:49:20	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	07:02:40	55.5583	-15.9042		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	07:02:45	55.5583	-15.9042	STATION139	PHA		
06/05/2018	07:04:21	55.5584	-15.9043		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	07:15:36	55.5584	-15.9044		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2018	07:50:42	55.5584	-15.9042		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	07:53:24	55.5583	-15.9042	TRANSIT5	PHA		
06/05/2018	08:30:36	55.6391	-15.9318	STATION140	PHA		
06/05/2018	08:52:33	55.6426	-15.9337		OPE	Mooring	Recovery
06/05/2018	09:12:36	55.6424	-15.9367	STATION141	PHA		
06/05/2018	09:49:04	55.6449	-15.9321		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
06/05/2018	10:11:03	55.6448	-15.9321		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
06/05/2018	10:27:58	55.6449	-15.932		OPE	MultiNet	End
06/05/2018	11:01:13	55.5782	-15.9139	STATION142	PHA		

06/05/2018	11:15:51	55.5583	-15.9041		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
06/05/2018	11:45:08	55.5587	-15.9041		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
06/05/2018	12:07:02	55.5588	-15.9042		OPE	MultiNet	End
06/05/2018	12:13:50	55.5562	-15.9058	TRANSIT6	PHA		
06/05/2018	13:06:58	55.4484	-15.8677	STATION143	PHA		
06/05/2018	13:46:03	55.4548	-15.8694		OPE	Mooring	Recovery
06/05/2018	14:17:18	55.455	-15.8681	TRANSIT7	PHA		
06/05/2018	14:51:36	55.5079	-15.8758	STATION144	PHA		
06/05/2018	14:57:05	55.5077	-15.8767		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	15:12:13	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2018	15:37:37	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	15:43:28	55.5077	-15.8767	STATION145	PHA		
06/05/2018	15:47:34	55.5077	-15.8768		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
06/05/2018	16:15:42	55.5077	-15.8773		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
06/05/2018	16:44:39	55.5075	-15.8767		OPE	MultiNet	End
06/05/2018	16:56:14	55.5077	-15.8766	STATION146	PHA		
06/05/2018	16:57:59	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	17:12:25	55.5075	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	17:27:36	55.5075	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	17:27:41	55.5075	-15.8766	STATION147	PHA		
06/05/2018	17:28:40	55.5075	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	17:43:07	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	17:58:04	55.5075	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	17:58:08	55.5075	-15.8766	STATION148	PHA		
06/05/2018	17:59:14	55.5075	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Begin

06/05/2018	18:14:21	55.5076	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	18:28:55	55.5075	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	18:29:05	55.5076	-15.8766	STATION149	PHA		
06/05/2018	18:30:09	55.5076	-15.8765		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	18:44:52	55.5076	-15.8765		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
06/05/2018	19:11:28	55.5075	-15.8765		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	19:33:03	55.5076	-15.8768	STATION150	PHA		
06/05/2018	19:35:17	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	19:50:13	55.5075	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	20:06:03	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	20:06:13	55.5076	-15.8767	STATION151	PHA		
06/05/2018	20:07:11	55.5076	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	20:21:37	55.5075	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	20:38:23	55.5075	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	20:38:32	55.5075	-15.8768	STATION152	PHA		
06/05/2018	20:40:14	55.5076	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	20:54:09	55.5076	-15.877		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	21:12:45	55.5076	-15.877		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	21:12:54	55.5076	-15.877	STATION153	PHA		
06/05/2018	21:14:36	55.5077	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Begin
06/05/2018	21:29:19	55.5074	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	Bottom
06/05/2018	21:46:19	55.5075	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	End
06/05/2018	21:46:30	55.5075	-15.8769	STATION154	PHA		
06/05/2018	21:47:52	55.5075	-15.8768		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
06/05/2018	22:01:53	55.5075	-15.8769		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom

06/05/2018	22:32:40	55.5076	-15.8766		OPE	CTD with samples	End
06/05/2018	22:32:52	55.5076	-15.8766	STATION155	PHA		
06/05/2018	22:42:57	55.5077	-15.8769		OPE	MultiNet	Begin
06/05/2018	23:11:59	55.5075	-15.8769		OPE	MultiNet	Start Heave
06/05/2018	23:40:42	55.5075	-15.8767		OPE	MultiNet	End
06/05/2018	23:40:54	55.5075	-15.8767	STATION156	PHA		
06/05/2018	23:54:22	55.5076	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	00:09:05	55.5075	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	00:25:32	55.5076	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	00:25:43	55.5076	-15.8768	STATION157	PHA		
07/05/2018	00:27:59	55.5076	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	00:42:32	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	00:59:04	55.5079	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	00:59:12	55.5079	-15.8768	STATION158	PHA		
07/05/2018	01:00:39	55.5079	-15.877		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	01:15:58	55.5078	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	01:31:43	55.5077	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	01:31:49	55.5077	-15.8765	STATION159	PHA		
07/05/2018	01:33:06	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	01:47:39	55.508	-15.8773		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	02:04:33	55.5077	-15.8762		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	02:04:39	55.5077	-15.8762	STATION160	PHA		
07/05/2018	02:06:23	55.5078	-15.8763		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
07/05/2018	02:20:27	55.5076	-15.8766		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
07/05/2018	02:48:59	55.5076	-15.877		OPE	CTD with samples	End

07/05/2018	03:07:16	55.5078	-15.8767	STATION161	PHA		
07/05/2018	03:14:38	55.5078	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	03:31:11	55.5077	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	03:48:15	55.5079	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	03:48:21	55.5078	-15.8767	STATION162	PHA		
07/05/2018	03:49:39	55.5078	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	04:07:09	55.5077	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	04:19:24	55.5076	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	04:19:30	55.5076	-15.8766	STATION163	PHA		
07/05/2018	04:21:14	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	04:35:57	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	04:50:37	55.5077	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	04:50:42	55.5077	-15.8767	STATION164	PHA		
07/05/2018	04:52:03	55.5078	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	05:06:20	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	05:21:23	55.5077	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	05:21:28	55.5077	-15.8767	STATION165	PHA		
07/05/2018	05:22:38	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
07/05/2018	05:36:50	55.5076	-15.8766		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
07/05/2018	06:01:35	55.5077	-15.8769		OPE	CTD with samples	End
07/05/2018	06:29:08	55.5075	-15.8765	STATION166	PHA		
07/05/2018	06:37:16	55.5074	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	06:51:47	55.5075	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	07:06:55	55.5077	-15.8765		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	07:07:00	55.5077	-15.8765	STATION167	PHA		
07/05/2018	07:08:08	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Begin

07/05/2018	07:22:21	55.5077	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	07:37:17	55.5076	-15.8768		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	07:37:21	55.5076	-15.8768	STATION168	PHA		
07/05/2018	07:38:26	55.5076	-15.8769		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	07:53:59	55.5077	-15.877		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	08:08:42	55.5079	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	08:08:53	55.508	-15.8766	STATION169	PHA		
07/05/2018	08:09:51	55.508	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	Begin
07/05/2018	08:24:51	55.5077	-15.8766		OPE	CTD	Bottom
07/05/2018	08:40:07	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD	End
07/05/2018	08:40:17	55.5076	-15.8767	STATION170	PHA		
07/05/2018	08:41:30	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
07/05/2018	08:56:10	55.5078	-15.8765		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
07/05/2018	09:21:33	55.5076	-15.8767		OPE	CTD with samples	End
07/05/2018	10:09:55	55.4285	-15.7757	STATION171	PHA		
07/05/2018	10:15:47	55.4285	-15.7758		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
07/05/2018	10:35:18	55.4286	-15.7756		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
07/05/2018	11:14:05	55.4283	-15.7758		OPE	CTD with samples	End
07/05/2018	11:39:08	55.448	-15.85	STATION172	PHA		
07/05/2018	11:50:14	55.4531	-15.8713		OPE	CTD with samples	Begin
07/05/2018	12:04:42	55.4531	-15.871		OPE	CTD with samples	Bottom
07/05/2018	12:33:26	55.4533	-15.8721		OPE	CTD with samples	End
07/05/2018	12:37:39	55.4539	-15.871	TURNING1	PHA		

Appendix 2 - Casino logbook

END